

THE THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGIONAL ECONOMIC SYSTEM

*Tursunova Aziza Xoshimovna,
Muhammad Qarshi branch of Tashkent
University of Information Technology
named after Muhammad al-Khwarazmi*

Abstract. *In this article, state regulation of the regional economy, its principles, improvement methods and mechanisms are studied.*

Keywords: *region, regional policy, regional economy, market, customs.*

Introduction. The reforms being implemented in our country to form a stable and effective economy are showing their results today. In particular, significant achievements have been made in a short period of time in implementing deep structural changes in the economy, ensuring growth in population incomes, strengthening effective foreign trade and investment processes, reforming agriculture, sustainably developing small business and private entrepreneurship, and strengthening the activities of the banking and financial system. Uzbekistan's prestige and position in the international economic arena are growing significantly and steadily. In this regard, the careful development of the socio-economic development strategy by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev, the clear and correct indication of the goals and objectives of economic reforms, and the ways to implement them, have made it possible to achieve significant achievements and milestones towards the main goal.

Main part. In the conditions of the development and improvement of the market economy, the issue of ensuring territorial balance acquires significant economic importance, in which the state's direct and indirect participation in ensuring balance is necessary. As is known, in the regulatory method of managing the economy, the state actively participates in ensuring territorial balance in the country through its social, economic and political mechanisms. In this paragraph, we will pay special attention to the economic mechanisms of the state for ensuring territorial balance. The basis of the composition of the economic mechanisms of the state in ensuring territorial balance is financial policy. Because financial policy is an important activity of the state, it is a set of economic relations aimed at the formation of financial resources and their distribution and effective use, taking into account the socio-economic development of the country. In the process of implementing these relations, the state pays special attention to ensuring territorial balance directly. It is worth noting that the state's financial policy embodies the budget, tax, customs and monetary policies aimed at the economic development of the country. The main direction of financial policy in

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ensuring regional balance is to increase the efficiency of the use of financial resources in the regions, to organize financial relations related to their redistribution between sectors of the financial system and to exercise control.

In addition, the main direction of financial policy, according to its purpose, also includes budget, tax, customs and monetary policies, which directly contribute to the full implementation of the goals and objectives set by the state. In particular, the main directions of budget policy in ensuring regional balance in the country include issues such as financial support for the budget system, creating conditions for socio-economic development, social protection of low-income strata of society, and supporting the financial stability of the country. There are such links in the economy in the country that are necessary for society as a whole, but whose interest in the financial situation of enterprises, organizations, and private entrepreneurs is not directly felt. These are also considered to be one of the main factors influencing the mechanism of state regulation of regional balance. These include infrastructure facilities in the country, raw materials and energy sectors, fundamental sciences, which usually do not bring material benefits to enterprises, organizations and private entrepreneurs, but require large capital investments with a long payback period at the expense of the state. Therefore, they are fully or partially transferred to the state and constitute the state sector of the economy. As a result of the large-scale privatization of state property in the transition economy, a sharp reduction in the state share, to a certain extent, is a condition of the economy. However, despite this, considering the long-term nature of this process and the important role it plays in the restructuring of the national economy and the state's role in ensuring territorial balance, some problems remain unresolved compared to those in countries with market relations.

It should be noted here that the production and distribution of social benefits is the main task of the state. Social benefits are goods and services provided to certain groups of the population or to society as a whole. They cannot be sold in pieces to individuals, as this may lead to a shortage of these products or services in the domestic market, which may lead to the development of some negative consequences. Legal order, state defense, environmental protection, public utilities, social programs, etc. are also included in them and play an important role in ensuring territorial balance by the state. Social programs play a significant role in social benefits. In the process of their implementation, the state provides the population with free education, health care, public utilities and other services. Many of these services can be divided and distributed entirely through the market system, but given their importance for the development of society, the state takes them on board and considers them as the main means of ensuring territorial balance. In this way, the state coordinates the distribution of resources in the economy and redistributes income.

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